

INVESTIGATING FUTURE CREATIVE PROFESSIONALS IN THE TRADITION OF THE REALISTIC SCHOOL OF FINE ARTS

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Abstract. *In this article, based on today's demand, a person with open eyes will definitely see the changes in education. The science of composition is considered the oldest of fine arts. Humanity appeared to paint. Through images, they express their dreams and thoughts. A clear example of this is the masterpieces of art found in Sarmishsay rock and other places.*

Keywords: *visualize, see proportions, eye, ear or eyebrow, symmetrical section, picture plane in composition, drawing, perspective and light-shadow laws, creating an image, drawing, interaction of elements, their proportions, expression of movement, general composition of texture, compositional device, external technical material in painting, coloristic and spatial systems.*

The science of composition is considered the oldest of fine arts. Humanity appeared to paint. Through images, they express their dreams and thoughts. A clear example of this is the masterpieces of art found on the Sarmishsay rocks and many other places. In addition, we know from history that during the time of Amir Temur, the attention to visual arts was extremely high, and the Samarkand school of visual arts had its influence on the culture of the peoples of the world.

The famous pedagogue-artist N.N. Ge said: "Always remember this law: To describe is to see proportions, so never see or describe parts separately. You need to describe not one eye, one ear or one eyebrow, but how these parts are located on the face and their mutual proportions. When describing these parts, always see them as a whole: always describe the symmetrical parts together and at the same time, both ears, both eyes, both cheeks..."

It is not for nothing that the secrets of creating a three-dimensional image of a being on the picture plane in composition will become known after getting acquainted with the laws of painting, perspective and light-shadow. It is for this reason that teaching the painting system for several centuries begins with teaching the basics of perspective and light and shade in depicting a work. Drawing is the mastery of the unique features and characteristic image of the object by seeing it in various changes depending on the environment. Seeing the highest peaks of fine art, learning to progress - creating an image, starting with painting. Painting is not only for artists who are an important basis of activity, but also the volumetric aspects of any image, whose activity is carried out in other forms of image creation, the interaction of the participating elements, their proportions, the expression of movement, the general composition of the texture are brought to a specific solution. The sense of feeling the spatial aspects of the existence that surrounds us also embodies an emotional content that is clear in its nature. A full sense of spatial space has a positive effect on a person. Often, a wide open spatial space evokes a feeling of freedom, joy and excitement in our body, and vice versa. Any image on a flat surface has spatial properties to one degree or another. For this reason, in the process of creating an artistic image, the problem of organizing spatiality in this image lies before every artist who creates an image. In order to solve this problem correctly, we will also touch upon the laws of perspective. When it comes to the role of composition in the

image, first of all, it is necessary to pay special attention to its main laws. In addition to the basic laws of composition, there are rules and methods that are important in revealing the pictorial "essence" of the plot, and they are technical tools in the organization of a plastic motif. They are aimed at the realization of new tasks faced by the new generations of artists that have arisen over the years to meet their needs and other methods and tools. Adherence to the general laws of composition is very important in creating a work belonging to any genre of painting, as well as theater, cinema and television. The importance of this or that rule depends on the type of art, the genre of the work, and, of course, the author's ability to use these tools effectively. Also, in this book, the artist on creating an artistic image, in order to understand the basis of the image that arises as a result of the creative process, we talk about this or that work of art. In this analysis, in some cases, we pay attention to the artistic aspects of the work, to its technical characteristics, external technical equipment, tools and methods in the compositional device, painting, coloristic and spatial systems.

The subject of composition as an educational subject was established much later than painting and coloring. The reason why composition is lagging behind as an educational subject is that painting has been the basis of visual lessons. It is still relevant. Creative development of an artist is impossible without solid mastery of this foundation of fine art.

The formation of composition as a science. It is inextricably linked to the fact that the process of learning to create a work is a really complex process, it requires creativity, knowledge, skill and originality, it is a more intuitive state.

The development and implementation of the national personnel training program in our country is of great importance in the process of education. Because training of national personnel and their comprehensive development along with training of highly qualified teachers-pedagogues, it serves as the main factor for providing education to the young generation at a high level. "We consider it our first priority to improve the activities of all links of the education and training system based on the requirements of today's times."

At present, in the rapidly developing conditions of science and technology, the intellectual scope of a person is growing extremely and scientific information due to the increasing number of people, it has become extremely necessary to maintain and develop the emotional state of people towards art.

President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev said, "It is clear to all of us that the cornerstone of development and the force that makes the country powerful and the nation great is science, education and upbringing. Our tomorrow, the bright future of our country is first of all closely related to the education system and the education we give to our children. We understand that it cannot be delayed or stopped even for a minute.

Today, it is necessary to further improve the quality of education, to use various methods in the educational process, to find new ways to educate young people in accordance with the requirements of the time. Based on the requirements, in order to regulate relations in the field of education, the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "ON EDUCATION" dated September 23, 2020, No. ORQ-637 generation, it is correct to consider it as another example of our country's high attention to education.

It can also be seen that in the following years, the attention to education and the interest in fine arts increased even more. The young generation is also following in the footsteps of their

teachers, making their worthy contribution to the recognition of the beauty of our country to the world through their works.

For example, we cannot always fully analyze the individual characteristics of the famous works created by the great artists of the past, as well as the examples of the works of contemporary artists, as well as the historical and social foundations of their works. For us, this is not an overall analysis of the direction and style of the works, but a conditional and limited one in a certain sense - the regularities in the image and color systems used by the artist in a particular work, the spatiality of the image, it is important to cover the analysis of the law, rule, method and means of composition, as well as the different ways of representation and expression. Each work analyzed was used only in the creation of the image is given as an example of certain necessary tools for the purpose of our topic of description and expression. Naturally, this element of the composition will certainly take other elements into its sphere of influence in the organization of the image and its composition. These aids, in turn, are given on the example of other works, and in some cases, on the example of the work in question. The purpose of this is that the artistic form and the medium that creates it is its language, It aims to exaggerate its elements as much as possible, to show its important place among other tools in a specific work, and to show its meaningful aspects in these works of art.

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